

EPIDEMIOLOGY AND SURGICAL OUTCOMES OF UNSTABLE THORACOLUMBAR JUNCTION FRACTURES

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Keywords

Spinal fractures
Thoracic vertebrae
Lumbar vertebrae
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Treatment outcome

ABSTRACT

This study aims to provide region-specific epidemiological data on unstable traumatic thoracolumbar junction (TLJ) fractures, perform descriptive and comparative analyses, and present objective findings regarding surgical outcomes. This single-center retrospective cohort study reviewed spinal surgeries performed between 2011 and 2020 at İnönü University, identifying 148 patients who met the study criteria. Evaluated parameters included age, sex, etiology, fracture type and level, Denis three-column and AO Spine classifications, surgical technique, graft type, fusion status, comorbidities, associated organ injuries, Cobb angle measurements, and length of hospital stay. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Of the 148 patients, 58.1% were male, with a mean age of 42.72 ± 17.58 years. Fractures were more frequent among individuals over 35 years of age. Falls from height constituted the leading etiology (52.7%), followed by traffic accidents (26.4%) and simple falls (18.2%). The most frequently affected vertebrae were L1 (46.6%) and T12 (27.7%). Fusion was achieved in 90.5% of cases, and fusion success did not significantly differ among the surgical techniques ($p > 0.05$). Thoracolumbar junction fractures—predominantly affecting young adult males following falls from height—highlight the need for region-specific preventive strategies, particularly in agricultural communities. The high prevalence of fractures resulting from low-energy trauma in older adults underscores the importance of age-tailored prevention programs. Patient-specific selection of surgical techniques remains essential for optimizing fusion outcomes, and the frequent coexistence of associated organ injuries emphasizes the value of a multidisciplinary approach. This study provides region-specific epidemiological insights that may support individualized surgical decision-making and guide public health policies.

INTRODUCTION

Traumatic spinal injuries are associated with substantial morbidity and mortality worldwide²⁰. Compared with other types of trauma, spinal and spinal cord injuries result in significant functional impairment, low return-to-work rates, and substantial psychosocial and physical burdens on society⁸. The prolonged and costly nature of treatment, associated workforce loss, and the increased psychological stress experienced by affected individuals further amplify the societal impact of these injuries^{18,24}. Studies have reported that individuals with spinal cord injuries experience a decline in social relationships and higher suicide rates^{6,26}.

Because traumatic injuries are largely preventable, epidemiological studies play a crucial role in identifying effective preventive strategies. While such research is widely conducted in developed countries, epidemiological data remain relatively limited in Middle Eastern regions^{21,29}.

The term thoracolumbar junction (TLJ) was first introduced by Stagnara in 1982 to describe the T10–L2 vertebral segment²². This region represents a transitional zone between the rigid, kyphotic thoracic spine and the more mobile, lordotic lumbar spine, making it particularly vulnerable to shear forces. Consequently, the TLJ is the most frequently affected region, accounting for approximately 70% of traumatic spinal fractures^{2,15}.

Although thoracolumbar fractures may also arise from metastatic, infectious, osteoporotic, or degenerative conditions, trauma remains the most common cause. Increasing industrialization, higher traffic density, greater building heights, and an aging population have all contributed to the rising incidence of traumatic spinal injuries¹¹. These fractures occur predominantly in young adult males, who constitute the demographic most frequently exposed to trauma^{12,32}.

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This study aims to provide a comprehensive, region-specific epidemiological dataset on unstable TLJ fractures based on a large patient series, to generate recommendations that may support patient management, and to compare the effectiveness of the surgical techniques employed. Therefore, our hypothesis was that no significant differences in fusion success or radiological correction would be observed among the various surgical techniques used.

METHOD

This study was designed as a retrospective, single-center observational cohort study. Patient records of all spinal surgeries performed in the Department of Neurosurgery at İnönü University between January 1, 2011, and May 1, 2020, were retrospectively reviewed. During this period, 1,385 spinal surgeries were identified, of which 166 involved traumatic thoracolumbar junction (TLJ) fractures.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Traumatic unstable fractures involving the T10–L2 levels
2. Traumatic etiology
3. Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score ≥ 14
4. Complete clinical and radiological data

Exclusion criteria:

1. Traumatic fractures outside the TLJ
2. Non-traumatic fractures
3. GCS ≤ 13
4. Incomplete archival records

After applying these criteria, 148 of the 166 patients met the study requirements and were consecutively included in the cohort; all analyses were based on these 148 patients. No a priori sample size or power calculation was performed; instead, a non-probability consecutive sampling approach was used, including all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria during the study period. In daily practice during the study period, the decision that a TLJ fracture was unstable and required surgical treatment was made by the attending spine surgeon based on fracture morphology, radiological findings, and patient-specific clinical characteristics. The evaluated parameters included age, sex, etiology, fracture type and level, Denis three-column classification, AO Spine classification, surgical technique, graft type, fusion status, comorbidities, associated organ injuries, Cobb angle measurements, and

length of hospital stay. The primary outcomes were (1) fusion success during follow-up and (2) radiological correction based on preoperative and postoperative Cobb angle measurements. In this study, traumatic unstable TLJ fractures were evaluated irrespective of osteoporosis status. Due to the retrospective design, objective osteoporosis assessment via DEXA was generally not feasible. Excluding osteoporotic patients would have produced an artificial cohort with only normal bone quality and reduced the representativeness of real-world trauma populations. Therefore, all patients presenting with traumatic TLJ fractures and treated with pedicle screw stabilization were included, whereas osteoporotic cases managed with kyphoplasty or cement augmentation solely for pain control were excluded.

Fusion success was evaluated based on the need for revision surgery during long-term follow-up. Revision procedures included surgeries performed for postoperative mechanical complications such as screw or rod breakage, implant failure, adjacent segment disease, or progression of scoliosis. Surgeries required due to technical errors during the initial procedure (e.g., screw malposition or inadequate decompression) were excluded. Patients who did not require revision surgery by the end of follow-up were considered to have achieved adequate fusion. No randomization was performed due to the retrospective design, and no blinding or masking methods were applied.

This study was approved by the İnönü University Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee – Health Sciences Scientific Research Ethics Board (Decision No: 2020/792; Session No: 10; Date: June 2, 2020). The requirement for informed consent was waived due to the retrospective nature of the study.

Statistical analysis

The distribution of variables was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests, and because the data did not follow a normal distribution, non-parametric tests were used. Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 22.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, median, percentage) were used to summarize the data.

Quantitative variables were compared using the Kruskal–

Wallis test, Mann–Whitney U test, and Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Qualitative variables were analyzed using the Chi-square test, Fisher–Freeman–Halton exact test, and one-way Chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

The study was conducted and reported in accordance with the STROBE guidelines for observational research.

FINDINGS

Our series included 148 patients who underwent surgery for traumatic unstable thoracolumbar junction (TLJ) fractures. Of these, 86 (58.1%) were male and 62 (41.9%) were female (Table 1). Patient ages ranged from 2 to 84 years, with a mean age of 42.72 ± 17.58 years. The mean age was 43.81 ± 17.83 years for males (range: 2–84) and 41.19 ± 17.25 years for females (range: 12–70). The length of hospital stay ranged from 2 to 101 days, with a mean of 13.60 ± 13.15 days and a median of 9 days.

A statistically significant difference in the distribution of fractures was observed across age groups ($p = 0.000$; $p < 0.05$). Patients over 35 years of age had a significantly higher fracture rate (60.8%) compared with those younger than 20 years (9.5%) and those aged 20–35 years (29.7%) ($p_1 = 0.000$, $p_2 = 0.000$; $p < 0.05$). Additionally, the 20–35 age group showed a significantly higher fracture frequency than the under-20 age

group ($p_1 = 0.000$; $p < 0.05$) (Table 1). Fractures were significantly more common in males (58.1%) than in females (41.9%) ($p = 0.049$; $p < 0.05$) (Table 1). Falling from a height was the most frequent etiology (52.7%), followed by traffic accidents (26.4%), simple falls (18.2%), and crush injuries (2.7%) (Table 2, Figure 1).

Table 1. Distribution of Traumatic TLJ Vertebral Fractures by Age and Gender

		n	%	p
Age	<20	14	9.5	0.000*
	20-35	44	29.7	
	>35	90	60.8	
Gender	Male	86	58.1	0.049*
	Female	62	41.9	

Chi-square test for one-sample design * $p < 0.05$

Table 2. Etiological Distribution of Traumatic TLJ Vertebral Fractures

Etiology	n	%
Simple fall	27	18.2
Fall from height	78	52.7
Traffic accident	39	26.4
Compression under load	4	2.7

Figure 1. Etiological distribution of traumatic TLJ fractures

A statistically significant difference in the distribution of frequent in patients older than 35 years (24.4%) compared with etiologies was observed among age groups ($p = 0.032$; $p < 0.05$). No other significant differences were detected among the remaining age groups ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3, Figure 2). Post hoc analysis showed that this difference was in etiology distribution were detected among the remaining age groups ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3). Simple falls were significantly more

Table 3. Etiological Distribution According to Age Groups and Gender

		Simple Fall n (%)	Fall from Height n (%)	Traffic Accident n (%)	Compression under load n (%)	p
Age	<20	2 (14.3%)	11 (78.6%)	1 (7.1%)	0 (0%)	¹ 0.032*
	20-35	3 (6.8%)	27 (61.4%)	14 (31.8%)	0 (0%)	
	>35	22 (24.4%)	40 (44.4%)	24 (26.7%)	4 (4.4%)	
Gender	Male	14 (16.3%)	49 (57%)	20 (23.3%)	3 (3.5%)	² 0.530
	Female	13 (21%)	29 (46.8%)	19 (30.6%)	1 (1.6%)	

¹ Chi-square test ² Fisher Freeman Halton Exact Test * $p < 0.05$

Figure 2. Etiological distribution of traumatic TLJ fractures by age group

No statistically significant differences were found in the distribution of etiologies between genders ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3, Figure 3).

According to Denis' three-column theory, 12.8% of fractures involved only the anterior column, 37.2% involved the anterior and middle columns, and 49.3% involved all three columns (anterior, middle, and posterior) (Table 4). Based on Denis' fracture classification, 46.6% of cases were burst fractures, 27% were flexion–distraction injuries, 19.6% were compression fractures, and 6.8% were fracture–dislocations (Table 4).

Regarding the fractured vertebral levels, 46.6% of cases involved L1, 27.7% T12, 14.2% L2, 7.4% T11, 3.4% T10, and 0.7% had simultaneous fractures of T12 and L1 (Table 4). According to the AO Spine classification, 33.8% of fractures were B2, 30.4% A3, 14.2% A4, 6.8% A1, 5.4% C, 3.4% A2, 3.4% B1, and 2.7% B3 (Table 4).

In terms of surgical techniques, 66.9% of patients underwent long-segment fixation, 27% long-segment fixation with additional pedicle screws at the fracture level, 4.1% short-segment fixation, and 2% short-segment fixation with additional pedicle screws (Table 4). Regarding graft use, 11.5%

of procedures were performed without grafts, 48% used (Table 4). Fusion was achieved in 90.5% of cases, while 9.5% allografts only, and 40.5% used both autografts and allografts did not achieve fusion (Table 4).

Figure 3. Etiological distribution of traumatic TLJ fractures by sex

Table 4. Distribution of Study Parameters

Parameter	Category	n	%
Fractured Columns According to Denis 3-Column Theory	Anterior	19	12.8
	Anterior + Middle	55	37.2
	Anterior + Middle + Posterior	73	49.3
Classification According to Denis	Burst fractures	69	46.6
	Flexion-distraction fractures	40	27.0
	Fracture-dislocations	10	6.8
	Compression fractures	29	19.6
Fractured Vertebra Level	L1	69	46.6
	L2	21	14.2
	T10	5	3.4
	T11	11	7.4
	T12	41	27.7
	T12 L1	1	0.7
Classification According to AO Spine	A1	10	6.8
	A2	5	3.4
	A3	45	30.4
	A4	21	14.2
	B1	5	3.4
	B2	50	33.8
	B3	4	2.7
	C	8	5.4
Surgical Technique	Long-segment fixation	99	66.9
	Long-segment + pedicle screws at fracture	40	27
	Short-segment fixation	6	4.1
	Short-segment + pedicle screws at fracture	3	2
Graft Usage	No graft	17	11.5
	Autograft + Allograft	60	40.5
	Allograft only	71	48
Fusion Status During Follow-up	Fusion not achieved	14	9.5
	Fusion achieved	134	90.5

At least one chronic illness or comorbidity was present in 45.9% of the patients. Although those with comorbidities had longer hospital stays, the difference was close to—but did not reach—statistical significance ($p = 0.07$; $p > 0.05$) (Table 5).

Table 5. Evaluation of Hospital Stay According to the Presence of Comorbidities

Presence of Comorbidity	Hospital Stay (days)	
	Mean±SD	Median
No	12.13±11.07	8
Yes	15.31±15.12	10
p	0.070	

Mann Whitney U test

Secondary thoracic pathologies related to trauma were absent in 72.3% of cases, while hemothorax was observed in 14.2%, pneumothorax in 10.8%, and other injuries such as rib fractures in 2.7% of cases (Figure 4, Table 6).

Figure 4. Distribution of concomitant thoracic surgical pathologies in patients with traumatic TLJ fractures.

Orthopedic pathologies secondary to trauma were absent in 70.9% of cases, while extremity fractures were present in 16.2%, scapular or clavicular fractures in 4.7%, and pelvic fractures in 8.1% of cases (Figure 5, Table 6).

Figure 5. Distribution of concomitant orthopedic injuries in patients with traumatic TLJ fractures.

Regarding general surgery-related pathologies, no trauma-associated injury was observed in 93.2% of cases, while 4.7% had retroperitoneal hematoma, 1.4% had renal hematoma, and 0.7% had liver or spleen rupture (Figure 6, Table 6)

Figure 6. Distribution of concomitant general surgical pathologies in patients with traumatic TLJ fractures.

Regarding intracranial pathologies, no trauma-related findings were observed in 89.2% of cases, while 10.8% had secondary intracranial pathology (Figure 7, Table 6).

Figure 7. Distribution of concomitant intracranial pathologies in patients with traumatic TLJ fractures.

Compared with preoperative Cobb angles, postoperative measurements showed a statistically significant decrease ($p = 0.001$). The mean absolute change was $-3.83^\circ \pm 12.66^\circ$, corresponding to a median reduction of 29% (Table 7, Figure 8).

Table 7. Evaluation of Changes Between Preoperative and Postoperative Cobb Angles

Parameter	Cobb Angles		p
	Mean±SD	Median	
Preoperative	16.48 ± 11.91°	14°	0.001*
Postoperative	12.65 ± 10.38°	10°	
Absolute Change (Δ, in degrees)	-3.83 ± 12.66°	-4°	
Percentage Change	24.39% ± 184.54%	-29%	

Wilcoxon sign test * $p < 0.05$

Figure 8. Comparison of preoperative and postoperative Cobb angles (mean ± SD).

Adequate fusion was achieved in 88.9% of long-segment additional screws. However, no statistically significant stabilizations, 95% of long-segment stabilizations with difference was observed among these techniques regarding additional screws at the fracture level, 100% of short-segment fusion success ($p > 0.05$) (Table 8). stabilizations, and 66.7% of short-segment stabilizations with

Table 8. Evaluation of Fusion Formation and Success Rates According to Surgical Technique

	Long Segment	Long Segment + Screw at Fracture	Short Segment	Short Segment + Screw at Fracture	p
Fusion Status	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	0.303
Fusion not achieved	11 (11.1%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	1 (33.3%)	
Fusion achieved	88 (88.9%)	38 (95%)	6 (100%)	2 (66.7%)	

Fisher Freeman Halton Exact test

No statistically significant difference was identified among observed in hospital length of stay across surgical techniques, the surgical techniques regarding the degree of change this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.068$; between preoperative and postoperative Cobb angles ($p > p > 0.05$) (Table 10). 0.05) (Table 9). Although a near-significant difference was

Table 9. Evaluation of Cobb Angle Change According to Surgical Technique

Surgical Technique	Cobb Angle Change (%)	
	Mean ± SD	Median
Long segment	8.25±160.83	-33.3
Long segment + screw at fracture	52.17±232.24	-27.27
Short segment	120.52±216.60	-12.17
Short segment + screw at fracture	-16.24±14.80	-7.60
P	0.176	

Kruskal Wallis test

Table 10. Evaluation of Hospital Stay According to Surgical Technique

Surgical Technique	Hospital Stay (days)	
	Mean ± SD	Median
Long segment	13.24±12.95	9
Long segment + screw at fracture	13.15±14.09	8
Short segment	24.0±10.02	26
Short segment + screw at fracture	10.33±5.50	13
p	0.068	

DISCUSSION

Consistent with previous reports on the substantial morbidity and mortality associated with traumatic spinal injuries^{7,20}, our findings confirm that thoracolumbar junction fractures constitute a frequent and clinically significant subset of these injuries. In this context, the demographic characteristics of our cohort closely parallel those described in the literature. Traumatic spinal injuries are more frequently observed in men, with reported rates ranging from 57.4% to 65.5%^{16,31}. With advancing age, the decline in bone mineral density renders even low-energy trauma sufficient to cause fractures^{13,16,19}. Aging is recognized as the strongest risk factor for traumatic spinal fractures, and in the elderly population, low-energy trauma constitutes the most common etiology¹⁶. Our study supports these observations, demonstrating that thoracolumbar junction fractures occur more frequently in men and that minor trauma increasingly contributes to fracture frequency with aging. In light of these findings, regular monitoring of bone health, implementation of environmental modifications, and public awareness programs aimed at preventing low-energy trauma are recommended to reduce fracture frequency in the elderly population.

The most common etiological factors underlying traumatic spinal injuries are traffic accidents and falls²⁰. While traffic accidents predominate in developed countries, falls from height are more frequently reported in developing

countries^{13,17}. A study conducted in Turkey reported that the most frequent causes were falls (56%) and traffic accidents (42%)¹. Our findings are consistent with these results, as falls from height accounted for 52.7% of cases in our series, followed by traffic accidents (26.4%), simple falls (18.2%), and injuries caused by heavy loads (2.7%). The agricultural socioeconomic structure of our region leads to a high rate of falls from height, particularly during agricultural activities such as falling from trees. These events together account for more than 50% of all etiological factors. This observation highlights the necessity of developing local health policies to reduce traumatic TLJ injuries. Our findings further emphasize that educational programs targeting agricultural workers, focusing on spinal fractures and their potential consequences, should be urgently integrated into official health policies.

Several studies have reported no statistically significant differences in clinical outcomes between alternative surgical techniques^{3,5,27,28}. Likewise, research comparing surgical strategies for thoracolumbar fractures has generally shown comparable effectiveness across different approaches^{9,30,33}. Offering a complementary perspective, Akesen emphasized that surgical success rates primarily reflect the surgeon's competence rather than the specific technique selected². Consistent with these observations, we also found no statistically significant differences among the four surgical techniques with respect to fusion success on long-term follow-up. Similarly, correction rates based on changes in Cobb angles

calculated from preoperative and early postoperative radiographs did not differ significantly between techniques. The large standard deviation observed for the percentage change in Cobb angle likely reflects the disproportionate impact of a small number of outliers on a heterogeneous cohort, including some surgical subgroups with relatively few patients; these percentage values should therefore be interpreted with caution. Taken together, these findings indicate that both long-term and early postoperative outcomes were comprehensively evaluated using complementary radiological and fusion-based measures, yet no clear superiority of any single technique could be demonstrated.

Overall, these results align with previous reports indicating no clear advantage of any particular surgical technique in terms of clinical outcomes. However, it should be recognized that comparisons made without standardizing parameters such as fracture level, fracture type, and patient-specific clinical characteristics carry a considerable risk of bias. As a methodological limitation, our study reflects the surgeon's ability to select the most appropriate surgical approach for each patient rather than objectively comparing the superiority of techniques. Therefore, the results should be interpreted with caution when comparing different techniques. In this context, our findings are in line with previous suggestions that surgical outcomes may depend more on appropriate patient- and fracture-specific decision-making than on the inherent superiority of any single technique². These observations underscore once again the importance of patient-specific, individualized surgery. Nevertheless, given the heterogeneity of patient populations and the diversity of surgical approaches, there remains a clear need for more extensive, highly standardized prospective studies in this field.

Concomitant organ injuries are frequently observed in traumatic thoracolumbar junction (TLJ) fractures. In such cases, second spinal fractures have been reported in 15%, neurological injuries in 10–15%, and intracranial injuries in 11.6% of patients^{4,14,23,25}. Specifically, in flexion–distraction fractures, liver or splenic rupture may accompany the spinal injury in up to 45% of cases¹¹. In our study, TLJ fractures were associated with extremity fractures in 16.2%, hemothorax in 14.2%, intracranial pathologies in 10.8%, pneumothorax in 10.8%, and pelvic fractures in 8.1% of cases. Other additional organ injuries were observed at rates below 5%. These findings

indicate that traumatic TLJ fractures cannot be regarded as isolated spinal pathologies; rather, they frequently coexist with other organ injuries and therefore necessitate comprehensive and multidisciplinary evaluation.

Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, because multiple organ injuries are common in trauma patients, cases that resulted in mortality before surgical intervention could not be included, restricting the study population to patients who survived long enough to undergo surgery. Second, the relatively low level of industrialization in our region and the agriculture-based economy centered on apricot and walnut cultivation led to a disproportionately high rate of fall-from-tree injuries compared with more industrialized regions, which may limit the generalizability of our findings. Third, owing to the retrospective design, objective assessment of osteoporosis with tools such as DEXA was not available in most cases, which partly constrained the detailed evaluation of low-energy trauma and underlying bone quality. In addition, surgical techniques were not randomized but selected according to fracture morphology and patient-specific clinical characteristics; therefore, our data should not be interpreted as an unbiased head-to-head comparison demonstrating the superiority of one technique over another. Nevertheless, the primary aim of this study was to describe real-world surgical outcomes of trauma-related unstable thoracolumbar junction fractures irrespective of specific factors such as osteoporosis. We therefore consider that, although these issues should be kept in mind when interpreting the data, they do not fundamentally alter the main clinical message of the study.

Strengths of the study

Our study provides a comprehensive analysis of traumatic thoracolumbar junction (TLJ) fractures by combining large-scale epidemiological data with an evaluation of the outcomes of different surgical techniques. By simultaneously examining etiological distribution, concomitant organ injuries, surgical strategies, fusion success, changes in Cobb angles, and length of hospital stay, it offers a multidimensional perspective that is directly relevant to clinical practice. This integrative approach yields clinically meaningful insights for individualized patient management and provides data that may help inform regional health policies.

To the best of our knowledge, this is one of the largest single-center series in Turkey involving surgically treated TLJ fractures and the first epidemiological study from the Eastern Anatolia Region. The largest previously published Turkish study in this field, conducted by Durmaz et al. in 2023, reported 287 patients, of whom only 138 underwent surgical intervention¹⁰. In terms of the number of surgically treated cases, our series therefore represents one of the most comprehensive cohorts reported to date in the national literature.

An additional strength of this study is that the operations were performed over an extended time period by several spine surgeons using comparable techniques. This reduces the likelihood that our results merely reflect the practice pattern or technical performance of a single surgeon and may enhance the external validity and real-world applicability of the findings. Taken together with the large patient cohort, regional specificity, and multidimensional analytic approach, this study may provide clinically and scientifically useful information, particularly for similar healthcare settings.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the epidemiological characteristics and surgical outcomes of patients with unstable traumatic thoracolumbar junction (TLJ) fractures were comprehensively analyzed. Our findings demonstrated that these fractures most commonly occur in young adult males and are predominantly associated with falls from height. In line with the agricultural profile of the region, the predominance of fall-related injuries indicates that targeted prevention strategies—particularly those focusing on work-related falls—could substantially reduce fracture frequency. These observations underline the need to translate epidemiological data into community awareness initiatives and region-specific health policies, and they further emphasize the importance of nationwide, large-scale epidemiological studies. The observation that different surgical techniques yielded comparable success rates indicates that treatment planning should prioritize individualized surgical approaches tailored to the patient's clinical and radiological characteristics rather than the choice of technique itself. In addition, the frequent occurrence of concomitant organ injuries in our cohort underscores the importance of systematic evaluation and a multidisciplinary management strategy in these patients. As one of the largest single-center surgical cohorts on

traumatic TLJ fractures in Turkey and the first epidemiological investigation from the Eastern Anatolia Region, this study provides a robust dataset that strengthens the scientific validity and generalizability of the results and clearly demonstrates the urgent need for health policies tailored to the unique risk profile of the region. Taken together, our findings may help to shape both routine clinical practice and regional public health strategies and provide a solid basis for future multicenter, prospective studies with standardized surgical protocols.

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None.

Conflicts of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Acar EY, Dişer DT. Cerrahi uygulanan vertebra kırıklarında klinik ve radyolojik sonuçların değerlendirilmesi [Internet]. 2012 [Web address and access date: <https://dSPACE.ankara.edu.tr/items/95635a4e-88c9-4243-906a-38792bed74e5>; accessed November 2, 2024].
2. Akesen B, Ozyalcin A. Torakolomber omurga kırıklarında konservatif yaklaşımlar. *TOTBID Derg* [Internet]. 2018;17 [Web address and access date: <https://dergi.citius.technology/Journal/PView/14344/totbid-dergi>; accessed November 2, 2024].
3. Altay M, Ozkurt B, Aktekin CN, Ozturk AM, Dogan O, Tabak AY. Treatment of unstable thoracolumbar junction burst fractures with short- or long-segment posterior fixation in Magerl type A fractures. *Eur Spine J*. 2007;16(8):1145–55.
4. Benson DR. Unstable thoracolumbar fractures, with emphasis on the burst fracture. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*. 1988;(230):14–25.
5. Boerger TO, Limb D, Dickson RA. Does canal clearance affect neurological outcome after thoracolumbar burst fractures? *J Bone Joint Surg Br*. 2000;82(5):629–35.
6. Cao Y, Massaro JF, Krause JS, Chen Y, Devivo MJ. Suicide mortality after spinal cord injury in the United States: injury cohorts analysis. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2014;95(2):230–5.
7. Cooper C, Atkinson EJ, O'Fallon WM, Melton LJ III. Incidence of clinically diagnosed vertebral fractures: a population-based study in Rochester, Minnesota, 1985–1989. *J Bone Miner Res*. 1992;7(2):221–7.
8. Daly MC, Patel MS, Bhatia NN, Bederman SS. The influence of insurance status on the surgical treatment of acute spinal fractures. *Spine*. 2016;41(1):E37–44.
9. Danisa OA, Shaffrey CI, Jane JA, Whitehill R, Wang GJ, Szabo TA, et al. Surgical approaches for the correction of unstable thoracolumbar burst fractures: a retrospective analysis of treatment outcomes [Internet]. *J Neurosurg*. 1995;83(6):977–83 [Web address and access date: <https://thejns.org/view/journals/j-neurosurg/83/6/article-p977.xml>; accessed November 2, 2024].
10. Durmaz M, Ezgü M, Evleksiz D, Karimzada G. Management of thoracolumbar fractures: clinical, functional, and radiological outcomes in a single institution. *J Turk Spinal Surg*. 2023;34:124–30.
11. Eastlack RK, Bono CM. Fractures and dislocations of the thoracolumbar spine. In: *Rockwood and Green's fractures in adults*. 6th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott, p. 1557–9; 2007.
12. Gertzbein SD. Multicenter spine fracture study. *Spine*. 1992;17(5):528–40.
13. Grivna M, Eid HO, Abu-Zidan FM. Epidemiology of spinal injuries in the United Arab Emirates. *World J Emerg Surg*. 2015;10:20.

14. Hu R, Mustard CA, Burns C. Epidemiology of incident spinal fracture in a complete population. *Spine*. 1996;21(4):492–9.
15. Inanmaz ME, Kurtoglu A. Torakolomber ve lomber omurga kırıklarına biyomekanik yaklaşım. *TOTBID Derg* [Internet]. 2018;17 [Web address and access date: <https://dergi.citius.technology/Journal/PView/934/totbid-dergi>; accessed November 2, 2024].
16. Liu B, Zhu Y, Liu S, Chen W, Zhang F, Zhang Y. National incidence of traumatic spinal fractures in China: data from China National Fracture Study. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2018;97(35):e12190.
17. Masood Z, Wardug GM, Ashraf J. Spinal injuries: experience of a local neurosurgical centre. *Pak J Med Sci*. 2008;24(3):368–73.
18. McKinley WO, Gittler MS, Kirshblum SC, Stiens SA, Groah SL. Medical complications after spinal cord injury: identification and management. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2002;83(1 Suppl 1):S58–64.
19. Min Y, Hui-Yun G, Hou-cheng Z, Yuan-long X, Wei J, Lin C, et al. The surgical treatment strategies for thoracolumbar spine fractures with ankylosing spondylitis: a case report. *BMC Surg*. 2019;19(1):99.
20. Niemi-Nikkola V, Saijets N, Ylipoussu H, Kinnunen P, Pesälä J, Mäkelä P, et al. Traumatic spinal injuries in Northern Finland. *Spine*. 2018;43(1):E45–50.
21. Otom AS, Doughan AM, Kawar JS, Hattar EZ. Traumatic spinal cord injuries in Jordan: an epidemiological study. *Spinal Cord*. 1997;35(4):253–8.
22. Ozbakir MO, Celik H. Torakolomber omurga travmalarına giriş: epidemiyoloji, yaralanma mekanizmaları, sınıflamalar ve instabilitenin değerlendirilmesi. *Turk Norosirurji Derg*. 2020;30(3):403–9.
23. Pagadpally Girish PG, Paparaja Murthy PM, Janhavi V. A clinico-epidemiological study of traumatic spine injuries in a rural tertiary care centre in India: our experience [Internet]. 2013 [Web address and access date: <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/20133343065>; accessed November 2, 2024].
24. Pagliacci MC, Celani MG, Zampolini M, Spizzichino L, Franceschini M, Baratta S, et al. An Italian survey of traumatic spinal cord injury. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2003;84(9):1266–75.
25. Pope MH, Wilder DG, Mattern RE, Frymoyer JW. Experimental measurements of vertebral motion under load. *Orthop Clin North Am*. 1977;8(1):155–67.
26. Post MWM, van Leeuwen CMC. Psychosocial issues in spinal cord injury: a review. *Spinal Cord*. 2012;50(5):382–9.
27. Sasso RC, Renkens K, Hanson D, Reilly T, McGuire RA Jr, Best NM. Unstable thoracolumbar burst fractures: anterior-only versus short-segment posterior fixation. *Clin Spine Surg*. 2006;19(4):242–8.
28. Siebenga J, Leferink VJM, Segers MJM, Elzinga MJ, Bakker FC, Haarman HJTM, et al. Treatment of traumatic thoracolumbar spine fractures: a multicenter prospective randomized study of operative versus nonsurgical treatment. *Spine*. 2006;31(25):2881–90.
29. Tuma MA, Acerra JR, El-Menyar A, Al-Thani H, Al-Hassani A, Recicar JF, et al. Epidemiology of workplace-related fall from height and cost of trauma care in Qatar. *Int J Crit Illn Inj Sci*. 2013;3(1):3–7.
30. Verlaan JJ, Diekerhof CH, Buskens E, van der Tweel I, Verbout AJ, Dhert WJA, et al. Surgical treatment of traumatic fractures of the thoracic and lumbar spine: a systematic review of the literature on techniques, complications, and outcome. *Spine*. 2004;29(7):803–14.
31. Wang H, Zhang Y, Xiang Q, Wang X, Li C, Xiong H, et al. Epidemiology of traumatic spinal fractures: experience from medical university-affiliated hospitals in Chongqing, China, 2001–2010. *J Neurosurg Spine*. 2012;17(5):459–68.
32. Weninger P, Schultz A, Hertz H. Conservative management of thoracolumbar and lumbar spine compression and burst fractures: functional and radiographic outcomes in 136 cases treated by closed reduction and casting. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg*. 2009;129(2):207–19.
33. Wood KB, Bohn D, Mehbod A. Anterior versus posterior treatment of stable thoracolumbar burst fractures without neurologic deficit: a prospective, randomized study. *Clin Spine Surg*. 2005;18(Suppl 1):S15–23.